

THE PURPOSE AND OBJECTIVES OF THE SUBJECT OF PRE-CONSCRIPTION MILITARY TRAINING

Axatov Samariddin Alikulovich

*Teacher of the military training center of the National University of Uzbekistan
named after Mirzo Ulugbek, major in reserve*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8013811>

Annotation: *In this article, the goal and mission of pre-conscription military training science is to prove that it is the only science that can instill in our youth a patriotic spirit and teach them to overcome the challenges they may face in the military service.*

Keywords: *pre-conscription military training, constitution, normative document, military, protection, Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, military training, military education, structure of the armed forces, security, state, democratic, republic, duty, defense.*

INTRODUCTION

In our country, great importance is attached to the training of military personnel, improving their military skills. The opening of military academies and military academies by type of army is a clear proof of our opinion. Protecting our borders with vigilance by our troops also raises the military spirit of our people. A truly independent state does this by not handing over its defense to others. Promoting the military knowledge inherited from our ancestors, teaching the secrets of martial arts in military schools are also effective factors in raising the general military spirit of the people, educating the military in a strong and courageous manner.

THE MAIN PART

When we bring up pre-conscription youth, we must first enrich the political consciousness of these young people. In this regard, we are based on the laws and regulations issued by our state. There are a number of laws and regulations of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which are governed by regulations. Examples are the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Law on Conscription and Military Service, the Law on Defense of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the Statutes and Laws of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In addition, the teaching of the subject of primary education in secondary schools and secondary special, vocational education institutions is one of the key factors in the patriotic nature of our youth. Our young people, who are entering the higher military educational institutions of the Ministry of Defense and preparing for military service in all types of military service of our Armed Forces, are preparing for conscription in secondary schools and secondary special, vocational education institutions. In the process, they receive the necessary training and information that interests them. Such an educational process must be carried out in collaboration with the teaching staff of secondary schools and secondary special, vocational education institutions in cooperation with the military leader and teachers of pre-conscription military training. Therefore, in carrying out such urgent tasks, it is important that the team of military faculties of the Pedagogical University fulfills its obligations and responsibilities for the training of military leaders and pre-conscription military training teachers. In this regard, especially in the organization of pre-service military education and the teaching of its methodology, with a deep understanding of the

essence of the reform strategy of our Armed Forces, the most modern teaching methods and the latest models of educational equipment use, as well as we must not overlook the new requirements of our rapidly changing times. The organization and methodology of pre-conscription military education is one of the basics of special military training of students. This subject will be included in the state exam as part of the "Pre-conscription military training Subject" methodology. The main purpose of teaching special subjects is to improve the military-pedagogical training of students and to develop practical skills in conducting basic pre-conscription military training. The study of this subject is in accordance with the requirements of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "General military obligation and military service", Regulations of the Republic of Uzbekistan on pre-conscription training of young people, Orders and directives of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Uzbekistan, patriotic education of students, Issues of preparation for service in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, principles of planning the educational process in the field of pre-service training (The science of pre-conscription military training), the use of new pedagogical technologies in the organization and conduct of pre-service training in all sections of the program of primary education in educational institutions, be able to use modern teaching aids, responsibilities of the director of the educational institution and the pre-conscription military training teacher, contact forms with partner organizations, pre-conscription military training is to provide students with sufficient knowledge and skills to know the requirements of the material base and be able to apply them in practice. During their studies, students must have a high level of political, moral and spiritual training, as well as the qualities of a defender of the Fatherland, necessary for the military leader to fulfill his obligations to prepare young people for service in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan. One of the important conditions today is to fill the military units and divisions of our Armed Forces with well-educated personnel, to pay special attention to their political, spiritual, moral and patriotic education. The formation and training of the above-mentioned qualities and qualities of the personnel should not be considered as the sole responsibility of military educational institutions, unit commanders and military commanders. It is known that commanders and commanders are responsible for the activities of their subordinates in the army. But when it comes to the formation of qualities and qualities, pre-military education is very important. In this regard, it is especially important to provide quality and effective pre-conscription military training in general education schools, secondary special and secondary vocational education institutions. As noted by our first president Islam Karimov, "Educational institutions have a special role in educating the younger generation to be loyal to the people, the motherland, faith, courage and bravery, highly qualified, highly spiritual people". Article 13 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "General military obligation and military service" on the teaching of "Pre-conscription military training" in secondary schools, secondary special and vocational education institutions is written as follows: "Pre-conscription military training, including civil defense training, is a compulsory subject in the curriculum and is taught by pre-conscription military training science teachers in secondary schools, starting with graduation year or classes." In addition, these priorities are reflected in the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the National Training Program", "On Defense" and orders and requirements of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is obvious that the task of creating a fast, well-equipped armed forces capable of reliably and effectively protecting the peace and tranquility of our country, envisaged in the strategy of military reform in the Armed Forces, which began in January 1999, is only the task of higher military educational institutions. Such an idea is a one-sided approach to the issue. Pre-conscription military training is very important in this event.

RESEARCH AND RESULTS

It is safe to say that the improvement and development of pre-conscription military training science, the conduct of a number of scientific studies on the goals and objectives of pre-conscription military training science, the vigilance of state borders by our troops are the result of our scientific work. Educating our youth in the spirit of patriotism is one of the most pressing issues of today. What should we pay attention to when educating our youth in the spirit of patriotism? What kind of scientific research should we do? The first issue is to convince our young people of the way our ancestors went. The second issue (education) is that if we can educate our youth in the spirit of patriotism, we can say that we have laid a solid foundation for the future. The third issue (teaching) is one of the most pressing. The more we educate our young people, the more they will regain their self-confidence. In educating our youth to be military patriots, we first and foremost teach them our national values. It will help educate our youth to be military patriots. We will increase their interest in the management of military equipment by correctly explaining the changes in science and technology, which have a great impact on the rapidly changing times. Pre-conscription military training science will help us with this. This article provides research on how to find the purpose and mission of the science by providing information about the purpose and mission of the subject of basic pre-conscription military training. It has been proved on the basis of theoretical knowledge that the subject of pre-conscription military training is an integral part of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Because this science is a science that helps to prepare the main reserve of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan and serves to fill it with knowledgeable, educated youth.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, the article provides information on the purpose and objectives of the subject of pre-conscription military training. In the introductory part of the article, it is noted that the Republic attaches great importance to the training of military personnel, improving their military skills, as well as the opening of military academies, military educational institutions by type of army. This is a clear proof of our opinion. The fact that the state borders are guarded by our own troops also raises the military spirit of our people. A truly independent state does this by not entrusting its defense to others. Promoting the military knowledge inherited from our ancestors, teaching the secrets of martial arts in military schools are also effective factors in raising the general military spirit of the people, educating the military in a strong and courageous manner.

I believe that this article will serve as a basis for the development of pre-conscription military training.

Bibliography:

1. "The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan". 1992
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education". 2020
3. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Defense". 2018
4. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On general military duty and military service". 2019
5. Curriculum "Pre-conscription military training for young people " 2017
6. "Regulations on pre-conscription military training of adolescents" 2014